

A PRACTICAL ANALYSIS OF STUDYING ADOLESCENT THINKING

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Abstract: the thinking process is considered a complex cognitive process. Comprehensive study and development of the issue of independent creative thinking will never lose its relevance. Creativity encourages a person to develop in all aspects.

Key words: creative thinking, society, problem situation, intellectual development, will, cognitive processes, experimental analysis, forms of thinking, information society.

The youth of independent Uzbekistan, as the largest stream of our society, occupies an important place in its socio-political, economic and spiritual life.

By developing independent-creative thinking and critical thinking in the mind of young people, they are quickly adaptable to rapidly developing life conditions and market economy relations: it serves them to make rational and correct decisions.

Usually, when a problem situation arises, a person encounters unexpected, unfamiliar, difficult to understand, unknown things and events. As a result of mental effort, the problematic situation becomes a problem of understanding by using the qualities of will. Therefore, the issue is based on the problematic situation and is closely related to it. As a result of the analysis of the problematic situation, thinking makes it clear and turns it into a problem that can be solved. So, here there is a closed chain of interconnected thinking: thinking → problem → issue.

Independent creative thinking in teenagers was studied using the "9 points" method. In our daily life, when we face complex tasks or tasks, we often face problems even by thinking about the instructions that are not given in the task. The following activity teaches students not to create artificial obstacles. For this, it is necessary to carefully listen to the given task instructions. Students will be given the following task. "Combine these 9 given points with such a speech that in the process of combining, your hand is not broken, and the line is not drawn a second time." After that, test-takers are given 20 pre-prepared blanks. 9 points will be expressed in it. If the examinee fails to solve the problem after making the prescribed attempts within 15 minutes, he will be given additional help.

Creative thinking and problem solving are interconnected cognitive processes. But it is absolutely impossible to turn creative thinking into a problem-solving tool. Therefore, it is appropriate to distinguish their subtleties. In particular, solving the problem is done only with the help of thinking, because there cannot and will not be any special way. Thinking, on the other hand, arises only when solving a problem. Therefore, thinking plays a key role in setting new issues, creating new problems, understanding them by others, and in other cases. Therefore, creative thinking is not only related to problem solving, but also very necessary in acquiring knowledge, understanding texts, critically analyzing things and events, etc.

The experiment conducted on the study of independent creative thinking in teenagers was analyzed as follows.

Table 1

Boys	1	2	3	4	5
$\sum xi$	101	167	124	68	22
X	3,6	5,9	4,7	3,5	2,2

Boys scored 3.6 on 1 points, 2-points 5.9, 3-points 4.7, 4-points 3.5, 5-points 2.2, the average score was determined.

Girls	1	2	3	4	5
$\sum xi$	156	142	77	75	21
X	6	5,2	3,6	4,1	2,1

Girls 1-point 6, 2-point 5.2, 3-point 3.6, 4-point 4.1, 5-point 2.1, the average score was determined.

Total scores for independent creative thinking;

The total score of boys is 19.9 points, the total score of girls is 21 points.

Percentages:

Boys: 77.54%

Girls: 84%

Boys	1	2	3	4	5
	3,6	5,9	4,7	3,5	2,2
	18,09	29,64	23,61	17,58	11,05

Girls	1	2	3	4	5
	6	5,2	3,6	4,1	2,1
	28,57	24,76	17,14	19,52	10

The percentage of each point is 18.0+%, 2 points 29.64%, 3 points 23.61%, 4 points 11.05%. In girls, 28.57% of 1 points, 24.76% of 2 points, 17.14% of 3 points, 19.52% of 4 points, 10% of 5 points were found.

Independent creative thinking in teenagers is developing well now. It can be seen from the results of the experiment that boys were evaluated with 19.9 points and girls with 21 points. This, in turn, constitutes a high indicator of 25 points, which is considered the highest score. The task given to the students for a limited time gave a positive result.

Independence of thought is required in the information society. In this regard, the opportunities given to young people in our country are incomparable. Effective use of the created conditions requires constant supervision by young people and their relatives, the results will be more successful.

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